

COMPARATIVE *IN VITRO* CYTOTOXICITY EVALUATION OF *AMRITHAMANJARI RASA* USING THE MTT ASSAY ON MOUSE FIBROBLAST (L929) CELL LINE

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda acknowledges that all substances can act as medicine when appropriately processed and administered. *Rasashastra*, the alchemical branch of *Ayurveda*, transforms potentially toxic materials such as metals and minerals into therapeutically beneficial and biocompatible forms through elaborate purification and incineration processes. *Amrithamanjari Rasa*, a classical *Khalwiya Rasayana* described in *Rasendra Sara Sangraha* under *Kasa Roga Adhikara*, contains ingredients such as *Shuddha Hingula* and *Shuddha Vatsanabha*, both categorized under Schedule E^[1] of the Drugs and Cosmetics Rules, 1945. Hence, scientific validation of its safety is essential. The present study evaluated the *in vitro* cytotoxicity of *Amrithamanjari Rasa* on mouse fibroblast (L929) cell lines using the MTT assay. Results revealed that while the standard drug doxorubicin exhibited concentration-dependent cytotoxicity with an IC₅₀ of 8.939 μM, *Amrithamanjari Rasa*

showed minimal cytotoxicity, with cell viability remaining above 80% even at the highest concentration tested (320 μg/mL). Since 50% inhibition of cell viability was not observed, an IC₅₀ value could not be determined. These findings indicate excellent biocompatibility and a wide safety margin for normal cells. The negligible cytotoxicity may be attributed to traditional *Shodhana* and *Bhavana* processes, which promote the formation of stable metal–

organic complexes, thereby reducing free metal ion toxicity. Thus, *Amrithamanjari Rasa* demonstrates a favourable safety profile, supporting its traditional claims of therapeutic efficacy and safe use.

KEYWORDS: *Amrithamanjari Rasa*, *Rasashastra*, Herbomineral formulation, MTT assay, Cytotoxicity, Biocompatibility.

INTRODUCTION

From ancient times, the concept that “everything in the universe can serve as medicine” has been deeply rooted in Ayurvedic philosophy, emphasizing that it is the dose and method of processing that determine whether a substance acts as a remedy or a toxin. Within Ayurveda, *Rasashastra* occupies a unique place, wherein substances that are inherently toxic including metals, minerals, and certain poisonous herbs are deliberately transformed through elaborate purification and incineration procedures to convert them into safe, bio-assimilable forms capable of producing profound therapeutic effects. This alchemical discipline of Ayurveda reflects a rational perspective that toxicity is not an inherent flaw of a substance, but is governed by its form, processing, and dosage.

Historically, *Rasoushadhis* have been valued for their rapid action, smaller dose, and long shelf life, distinguishing them as unique contributions of Ayurveda to global medical knowledge. However, in recent decades, concerns have arisen regarding the presence of heavy metals such as Mercury, Lead, and Arsenic in certain Ayurvedic formulations. Modern toxicologists often associate these elements with systemic, renal, and neurotoxic effects when consumed in their raw or improperly processed forms. In contrast, Ayurvedic scholars emphasize that the safety and efficacy of these substances depend not on their elemental nature, but on the chemical transformations they undergo during proper pharmaceutical processing.

In this context, it is essential to establish the safety of herbomineral formulations through systematic and scientifically designed experimental evaluations. Modern analytical and biological assessment tools provide reliable means to verify the safety and compatibility of such preparations. Among the various parameters employed in evaluating the safety of medicinal substances, cytotoxicity assessment holds a fundamental position. *In vitro* cytotoxicity assays serve as vital preliminary screening methods to identify any potential harmful effects of a formulation on normal, healthy cells before advancing to *in vivo* toxicity

studies or clinical evaluations. These assays evaluate parameters such as cell viability, membrane integrity, and metabolic activity, thereby providing valuable insights into whether a substance induces toxic effects on normal cells. In modern pharmacological research, *in vitro* cytotoxicity testing is regarded as an ethical, economical, and time-efficient approach, as it minimizes the need for extensive animal experimentation while offering reliable indicators of biocompatibility. Among the various *in vitro* methods available for evaluating cytotoxicity, the MTT assay has emerged as one of the most widely accepted, sensitive, and reproducible techniques in toxicological and pharmacological research. The MTT assay, first described by Mosmann in 1983, is a colorimetric method that measures the metabolic activity of cells as an indicator of their viability, proliferation, and cytotoxic response.^[1] The principle of the assay is based on the ability of mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzymes in viable cells to reduce the yellow tetrazolium salt, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT), into insoluble purple formazan crystals. These crystals are subsequently solubilized, and the resulting coloured solution is quantified spectrophotometrically at 570 nm, where the absorbance value is directly proportional to the number of metabolically active cells.^[1]

The present study focuses on *Amrithamanjari Rasa*, a classical herbomineral formulation described in *Rasendra Sara Sangraha* under *Kasa Roga Adhikara*.^[2] It is a *Khalwiya Rasayana* (formulation prepared by trituration in a mortar and pestle), composed of *Shuddha Hingula*, *Shuddha Vatsanabha*, *Pippali Churna*, *Maricha Churna*, *Shuddha Tankana*, and *Jathikoshha Churna*, which are subjected to levigation with *Jambeera Swarasa*. Traditionally, this *yoga* is indicated in *Pancha Vidha Kasa*, *Swasa*, *Jeerna Jwara*, *Amavata*, *Agnimandya*, and *Ajeerna*, indicating its broad-spectrum therapeutic efficacy.^[2] Both *Hingula* and *Vatsanabha* are recognized as toxic substances and are included under Schedule E(1) of the Drugs and Cosmetics Rules, 1945, framed under the Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940, as per Rule 161(2), which enumerates poisonous drugs of mineral and vegetable origin used in Ayurvedic formulations. Therefore, scientific evaluation of the safety profile of such herbomineral formulations becomes essential to substantiate their traditional claims and ensure safe therapeutic use. In this context, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the *in vitro* cytotoxicity of *Amrithamanjari Rasa* using the MTT assay on mouse fibroblast (L929) cell lines, with the objective of establishing its safety profile.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Pharmaceutical Preparation of *Amrithamanjari Rasa*

Genuine raw materials for *Amrithamanjari Rasa* were sourced from authenticated suppliers, including home-grown sources in Theerthahalli, Amrit Kesari Ayurvedic Raw Drug Depot (Bengaluru), and Siddheswara Drugs (Karalmanna, Palakkad). *Shuddha Hingula* was prepared through seven *Bhavanas* with freshly expressed *Ardraka Swarasa*.^[2] *Vatsanabha* was detoxified by immersion in fresh *Gomutra* for three days with daily renewal, followed by peeling, washing, and shade drying.^[3] *Tankana* was purified by gentle *Bharjana* to obtain a light, porous material, while *Maricha*, *Pippali*, and *Jatikosha* were cleaned, shade-dried, and finely sieved (120 mesh). Equal quantities (45 g each) of the purified ingredients were triturated with 280 ml of *Jambeera Swarasa* to achieve a uniform mass, which was rolled into *Ratti-pramana Vatis* (approximately 125 mg), shade-dried, and stored in airtight containers for further evaluation.

2. Experimental Study: *In vitro* Cytotoxicity by MTT Assay^[1]

The *in vitro* cytotoxicity evaluation (MTT assay) was carried out at Skanda Life Sciences, Sunkadakatte, Bengaluru.

2.1. Test Formulation and Reagents

The cytotoxicity of *Amrithamanjari Rasa* was evaluated using the MTT assay on mouse fibroblast (L929) cell lines. The prepared tablets were finely powdered using a sterile mortar and pestle. Due to the insoluble nature of the herbomineral formulation in aqueous solvents, Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) was employed as a crucial vehicle to create a stable dispersion of the compound. A primary stock solution was prepared at a concentration of 32 mg/mL by dissolving the powder in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). This stock solution was subsequently diluted in complete cell culture medium to create a working stock of 3.2 mg/mL, which was then serially diluted to obtain a concentration range of 5-320 µg/mL for treatment. Doxorubicin (1.56-100 µM) was used as the positive control, while cells maintained in culture medium alone served as the negative control. Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), Penicillin-Streptomycin, Trypsin-EDTA, Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS), and MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) reagent were procured from Sigma-Aldrich and Himedia Laboratories.

2.2. Cell Line and Culture Conditions

L929 mouse fibroblast cells, obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, CCL-1) were used for MTT assay. The L929 cell line, derived from normal mouse connective tissue, represents a well-established model for cytotoxicity testing according to international standards (ISO 10993-5). These cells are particularly valuable for safety assessment studies due to their sensitivity to toxic substances and their frequent use as a reliable indicator of biocompatibility in normal, non-cancerous mammalian cells.

L929 cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 IU/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL streptomycin. The cells were maintained at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ until they reached confluency. For subculturing, the cells were dissociated using 0.05% trypsin-EDTA and centrifuged at 1,000 rpm for 5 minutes. The resulting supernatant was carefully discarded, and the cell pellet was gently resuspended in 2 mL of complete DMEM. Cell viability was assessed using Trypan blue exclusion method, and a homogeneous single-cell suspension was prepared at a density of 5×10^5 cells/mL for subsequent experiments.

2.3. Cell Seeding

For cell seeding, a 96-well microtiter plate was systematically pre-labelled to ensure proper identification of experimental conditions. Each well received 100 µL of the prepared cell suspension, containing approximately 30,000-50,000 cells, to establish consistent seeding density across all experimental groups. The seeded plates were subsequently incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ for 24 hours, allowing for complete cell attachment and stabilization prior to experimental treatments.

2.4. Treatment with Test compounds

Following the 24-hour incubation period for cell attachment, the culture medium was carefully aspirated from all wells. The adherent cell monolayer was then gently rinsed with plain medium to remove any non-adherent cells and residual serum components. Subsequently, 100 µL of the respective test samples, including *Amrithamanjari Rasa* at various concentrations, Doxorubicin as positive control, or vehicle control, were added to their pre-designated wells. The treatment plates were then incubated for an additional 24 hours at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere to allow for compound exposure and potential cytotoxic effects.

2.5. MTT Assay

Upon completion of the 24-hour drug exposure period, the test solutions were carefully aspirated from all wells. Subsequently, 100 μL of MTT reagent, prepared at a concentration of 0.4 mg/mL in phosphate-buffered saline, was introduced into each well. The plates were then incubated for 4 hours at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ environment to permit viable cells to reduce the yellow tetrazolium salt into insoluble purple formazan crystals.

2.6. Solubilization of Formazan Crystals

The MTT solution was removed following the 4-hour incubation period. Each well then received 100 μL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to dissolve the Formazan crystals. To achieve complete solubilization and uniform colour development, the microtiter plate was gently agitated on an orbital shaker for 10-15 minutes.

2.7. Measurement of Absorbance and Data analysis

The optical density of the solubilized formazan product was quantified at 590 nm using a multimode microplate reader (SpectraMax i3X, Molecular Devices). The percentage of growth inhibition for each treatment concentration was subsequently calculated using the formula

% Inhibition = $[(\text{OD}_{\text{control}} - \text{OD}_{\text{sample}}) / \text{OD}_{\text{control}}] \times 100$, where OD_{control} represents the optical density of untreated control cells and OD_{sample} corresponds to the optical density of cells exposed to various concentrations of *Amrithamanjari Rasa*.

2.8. Determination of IC₅₀ Value

The half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) was determined by constructing a dose-response curve through nonlinear regression analysis. This analysis was based on a sigmoidal curve fit model, where the concentration of *Amrithamanjari Rasa* required to inhibit 50% of cell viability was calculated. The IC₅₀ values were computed using GraphPad Prism software (Version 5.0, GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA).

RESULTS

The MTT assay demonstrated that Doxorubicin (Standard) exhibited marked concentration-dependent cytotoxicity against L929 fibroblast cells across the tested range (1.56–100 μM). The percentage inhibition of cell viability increased progressively from 18.17 \pm 3.27% at 1.56 μM to 88.94 \pm 1.72% at 100 μM . Correspondingly, cell viability declined from 81.83% at the lowest concentration to 11.06% at the highest. The calculated IC₅₀ value for Doxorubicin

was 8.939 μM , confirming its potent cytotoxic effect on normal fibroblast cells and validating the sensitivity of the assay system.

In comparison, *Amrithamanjari Rasa* exhibited minimal cytotoxic effects on L929 mouse fibroblast cells across the tested concentration range (5–320 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). At the lowest concentration of 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, cell viability was $94.26 \pm 5.46\%$, while at the highest concentration of 320 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, viability remained at $82.74 \pm 2.37\%$. The percentage inhibition increased with concentration, from $5.74 \pm 5.46\%$ at 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to $17.26 \pm 2.37\%$ at 320 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Since the formulation did not reach 50% inhibition at any tested concentration, an IC_{50} value could not be determined. These results indicate that *Amrithamanjari Rasa* has excellent biocompatibility and negligible cytotoxicity toward normal fibroblast cells.

Table number 1: Average % inhibition and Cell viability of Standard(Doxorubicin) drug in L929 cells.

Concentration of Standard-Doxorubicin in μM	OD 1 at 590nm	OD 2 at 590nm	% Inhibition (Replicate 1)	% Inhibition (Replicate 2)	Average % Inhibition	$\pm\text{SD}$	Average % of viability
1.56	0.978	0.987	20.49	15.86	18.17	3.27	81.83
3.13	0.788	0.792	35.93	32.48	34.21	2.44	65.79
6.25	0.624	0.656	49.26	44.08	46.67	3.67	53.33
12.5	0.542	0.528	55.93	54.99	55.46	0.67	44.54
25	0.396	0.398	67.80	66.07	66.94	1.23	33.06
50	0.285	0.296	76.83	74.77	75.80	1.46	24.20
100	0.121	0.144	90.15	87.72	88.94	1.72	11.06
Standard showed IC_{50} value of 8.939 μM against L929 cells							

Table number 2: Average % inhibition and Cell viability of Amrithamanjari rasa in L929 cells.

Concentration of <i>Amrithamanjari</i> rasa extract in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	OD 1 at 590nm	OD 2 at 590nm	% Inhibition (Replicate 1)	% Inhibition (Replicate 2)	Average % Inhibition	$\pm\text{SD}$	Average % of viability
5	1.112	1.151	9.59	1.88	5.74	5.46	94.26
10	1.105	1.135	10.20	3.24	6.72	4.92	93.28
20	1.081	1.083	12.11	7.67	9.89	3.14	90.11
40	1.055	1.056	14.24	9.97	12.10	3.02	87.90
80	1.039	1.043	15.53	11.08	13.30	80	86.70
160	1.019	1.007	17.15	14.14	15.64	2.13	84.36
320	0.997	0.990	18.94	15.59	17.26	2.37	82.74
IC_{50} value could not be determined since inhibition did not reach 50%							

Figure 1: Dose response curve of Standard(Doxorubicin) on L929 cells.

Figure 2: Dose response curve of Amrithamanjari rasa on L929 cells.

DISCUSSION

The evaluation of *Amrithamanjari Rasa* on L929 fibroblast cells revealed a notably low cytotoxic profile, indicating excellent biocompatibility and a high margin of safety for normal cells. While a mild, concentration-dependent increase in inhibition was observed, this response was minimal in a biological context. The increase in inhibition from approximately 5% to 17% over a 64-fold concentration range (from 5 µg/mL to 320 µg/mL) is not indicative of a potent cytotoxic effect. Instead, this slight trend is likely due to normal cellular stress responses when exposed to very high concentrations of any substance, rather than a specific toxicological mechanism. Since the extract of the formulation did not reach 50% inhibition at any concentration within the broad range tested, it demonstrates that its therapeutic window is

likely very wide. This means that concentrations required for a desired therapeutic effect are expected to be substantially lower than those that would pose any risk to normal cells.

The minimal cytotoxicity observed for *Amrithamanjari Rasa* can be explained by multiple factors. Traditionally, *Rasa* formulations undergo a meticulous *Shodhana* (purification) process, which converts toxic metals into stable, inert, and therapeutically safe forms. This transformation markedly reduces the bioavailability of free metal ions that are typically responsible for inducing oxidative stress and cellular damage. In the present study, cell viability consistently remained above 80% across all tested concentrations, which is widely accepted as the threshold for non-cytotoxicity in *in vitro* assays. The maintenance of such high viability, even at the maximum concentration of 320 µg/mL, indicates that *Amrithamanjari Rasa* exerts negligible cytotoxic effects on normal fibroblast cells.

Furthermore, the safety of *Amrithamanjari Rasa* can also be linked to the role of *Jambira Swarasa* (lemon juice) used during the *Bhavana* (trituration) process. *Jambira Swarasa* is rich in citric acid, ascorbic acid, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds, which contain multiple carboxyl (–COOH) and hydroxyl (–OH) functional groups capable of interacting with metal ions. During *Bhavana*, continuous trituration brings the metallic particles into close contact with these organic constituents, promoting chelation or complexation between the metal ions and organic molecules. This interaction results in the formation of stable metal–organic complexes, where the metal ions become tightly bound within an organic matrix. Such chelation stabilizes the metallic particles, prevents uncontrolled oxidation or aggregation, and significantly reduces the availability of free, reactive metal ions that could otherwise induce oxidative stress or cytotoxic effects. The resulting metal–organic interface acts as a protective barrier, limiting the release of ionic species under physiological conditions.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the present study clearly demonstrate that *Amrithamanjari Rasa* exhibits excellent biocompatibility toward normal fibroblast (L929) cells, even at higher tested concentrations. The formulation maintained more than 80% cell viability across all tested doses, indicating its safety and non-toxic nature *in vitro*. The absence of a measurable IC₅₀ value further confirms that *Amrithamanjari Rasa* does not exert any significant inhibitory effect on normal cell proliferation. Therefore, *Amrithamanjari Rasa* can be concluded to possess an excellent *in vitro* safety margin for normal cells. The results validate its traditional use and suggest a wide therapeutic window, indicating that concentrations required for its

intended pharmacological activity are likely to be well below those that would pose a risk to normal cellular function.

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